

Collaboration Platform

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Working across the expanse of Europe in international and transdisciplinary context requires a shared platform to share, store, and communicate.

Benefits

While e-mails are a useful universal tool to communicate a consortium also needs means to collaborate and share data efficiently, which is where collaboration platforms come in.

Practical recommendations

While one-time data exchange services like Dropbox and Wetransfer exist they make less than ideal digital platforms to collaborate with. What you are looking for is a stable long-term platform that can store data and potentially allow live multi-user manipulation of files. There are several things to consider.

Accessibility

While most organisations have access to common platforms such as [Google Drive](#), [Sharepoint](#), or Monday, take into account that not all partners do. Especially smaller practice partners may not have pre-existing access to (common) digital platforms. Please consider hosting them through guest accounts.

Cybersecurity

When it comes to online collaboration platforms there are many options. However, mind that not all options are suited for each type of partner. Especially public organisations may be restricted in which platforms they are allowed to use.

Costs

Google Drive is free for personal use, and can be used in a pinch by partners, while both Sharepoint and the professional version of Google Drive are paid services. While we would love to be able to recommend a complete free, high security, universal digital solution, they do not exist.

Please engage your consortium on time on this topic, make an inventory of the digital platforms they are used to work with, and find a suitable consensus. If certain partners lack access, consider how to provide them with access (equitable means to participate) during the project.

The PREMIERE project does not claim ownership of the tools referenced herein; credit belongs to their respective creators.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Collaboration within an equitable digital co-working space.

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Sharepoint](#)

[Google Drive](#)

**right click to open*